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Experiments with 'phase bunching' for the IDT preprocessing

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The first 20 frames of the IDT data simulated by ESTEC (letter by S Vaghi 1985 April 2, Run 2 - Photon noise only) were analysed in four ways:

- (A) Solution of the rigorous ML equations, with a sufficient number of iterations to guarantee convergence in all cases. This is the reference solution against which the others are compared.
- (B) Unweighted least-squares estimation of the Fourier coefficients.
- (C) Same as (B), but followed by a single iteration of the ML eqs.
- (D) Same as (C), but performed on the 'phase-bunched' counts (the algorithm described below) and using a successively larger number of bins (from 8 to 64).

The parameters estimated in each method are b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5 in

$$N_\ell \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos H_\ell + b_3 \sin H_\ell + b_4 \cos 2H_\ell + b_5 \sin 2H_\ell \quad (1)$$

where $\{N_\ell, H_\ell; \ell = 1 \rightarrow L\}$ are the given arrays of photon counts (N) and reference phases (H). The reference phase is defined such that $H = 0$ at the frame mid-time. Since the scan velocity ($v = 168.75$ arcsec/s) is constant in these simulations, we have

$$H_\ell = 2\pi(T_\ell - T_k)v/s \quad (2)$$

with T_ℓ = sample mid-time, T_k = frame mid-time, $s = 1.208$ arcsec.

Phase bunching

This is a simplified version of the algorithm I proposed in 1980 Feb 22 (Further details ...). The phase interval $[0, 2\pi[$ is divided in M equal intervals $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. Given that all $H_\ell \in [0, 2\pi[$, we assign sample ℓ to bin number

$$m = \text{INT}(H_\ell M/2\pi) \quad (3)$$

Then let

$$w_m = \sum_{\ell \in m} 1 \quad (4a)$$

$$\bar{H}_m = \sum_{\ell \in m} H_\ell / w_m \quad (4b)$$

$$\bar{N}_m = \sum_{\ell \in m} N_\ell / w_m \quad (4c)$$

be respectively the weight of each bin (= number of samples assigned to it), the mean reference phase and the mean count per bin. The estimation then uses the model

$$\bar{N}_m \sim I_m \equiv b_1 + b_2 \cos \bar{H}_m + b_3 \sin \bar{H}_m + b_4 \cos 2\bar{H}_m + b_5 \sin 2\bar{H}_m \quad (5)$$

weighted by w_n [i.e., as if the equation (5) was repeated w_n times]. The ML equations for the correction to $\underline{b} = (b_1 \ b_2 \ b_3 \ b_4 \ b_5)'$ are thus

$$\left[\sum_m \underline{f}_m \underline{f}_m' w_m / I_m \right] \Delta \underline{b} = \sum_m \underline{f}_m (\bar{N}_m - I_m) w_m / I_m \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{f}_m = (1 \ \cos \bar{H}_m \ \sin \bar{H}_m \ \cos 2\bar{H}_m \ \sin 2\bar{H}_m)'$.

Output

For easy comparison between the results, the Fourier coefficients $b_1 \dots b_5$ were converted to fluxes and positions (in Hz and mas) according to

$$I_0 = b_1 / \Delta t \quad (7a)$$

$$I_1 = (b_2^2 + b_3^2)^{1/2} / \Delta t \quad (7b)$$

$$I_2 = (b_4^2 + b_5^2)^{1/2} / \Delta t \quad (7c)$$

$$p_1 = (s/2\pi) \text{ATAN2}(-b_3, b_2) \quad (7d)$$

$$p_2 = (s/4\pi) \text{ATAN2}(-b_5, b_4) + ns/2 \quad (7e)$$

with $\Delta t = 1/1200$ s and $s = 1208$ mas. In the last equation, the integer n is chosen to make $|p_1 - p_2| < s/4$. Then the results of (B), (C), and (D) were compared with (A) by forming the flux ratios (I_{1B}/I_{1A} , etc) and

position differences ($p_{2B} - p_{2A}$, etc). Finally the average and rms dispersion of each quantity among the 70 observations were computed. For the position errors, a weighted mean of the first and second harmonics was also computed,

$$p_0 = 0.627 p_1 + 0.373 p_2 \quad (8)$$

Results

Method	$\langle I_0./I_{0A} \rangle$	$\langle I_1./I_{1A} \rangle$	$\langle I_2./I_{2A} \rangle$	----- rms values -----		
				$(p_0.-p_{0A})$	$(p_1.-p_{1A})$	$(p_2.-p_{2A})$
B	0.99998	1.00063	1.00441	2.07 mas	1.13 mas	3.80 mas
C	1.00000	0.99940	0.99941	0.06	0.03	0.20
D, 12 bins	0.99998	0.98812	0.95470	2.51	1.77	5.06
D, 16 bins	1.00000	0.99225	0.96905	1.43	0.90	3.36
D, 24 bins	1.00000	0.99741	0.98781	1.09	0.81	2.16
D, 32 bins	1.00000	0.99730	0.98797	0.82	0.55	1.63
D, 36 bins	0.99999	0.99778	0.99349	0.70	0.47	1.46
D, 48 bins	1.00000	0.99912	0.99827	0.47	0.34	0.96
D, 64 bins	1.00000	0.99887	0.99617	0.35	0.30	0.68

Conclusions

1. The unweighted least-squares estimate (B) differs from the ML estimate by a few mas rms and should not be used.
2. The truncated ML estimate (one iteration only), method C, differs very little from the true ML estimate, and it seems completely justified to accept this simplification.
3. The 'phase bunching' has two very significant effects on the results:
 - The modulated fluxes (and hence M_1 and M_2) are systematically underestimated. The bias factor seems to be close to $\text{sinc}(\pi/M)$ and $\text{sinc}(2\pi/M)$ for the 1st and 2nd harmonic. Thus a corresponding correction factor should be applied on the results.
 - The rms dispersion of the position estimates due to the bunching is roughly inversely proportional to the number of bins (cf. Figure 1). For an acceptable dispersion (e.g. < 1 mas on both harmonics) one needs ≥ 48 bins.

Figure 1. Rms position dispersion caused by the phase bunching algorithms, as function of the number of bins.